

Complexes of Uranium(IV) and Thorium(IV) with α -Picolinic Acid, Nicotinic Acid, Anthranilic Acid and N-Phenylanthranilic Acid

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Stable U(IV) and Th(IV) complexes with the title ligands have been synthesised from $U(OAc)_4$ and $Th(OAc)_4$. Magnetic susceptibilities, IR and reflectance spectra of U(IV) and IR spectra of Th(IV) complexes have been studied which indicate eight coordination for U(IV) in these chelates.

U(IV) and Th(IV) complexes with 8-hydroxyquinoline, 8-OH-7-iodoquinoline-5-sulphonic acid, quinaldine acid, pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid,¹ 1-OH-2-naphthoic acid, 3-OH-2-naphthoic acid² and thiophene-2-carboxylic acid,³ have been synthesised and characterised recently. Under present investigations complexes of U(IV) and Th(IV) with the title ligands have been prepared and characterised on the basis of IR, electronic and magnetic susceptibility data.

Experimental

$U(OAc)_4$ and $Th(OAc)_4$ were prepared as reported in literature^{4,5}. α -Picolinic acid (Kochlight), nicotinic acid (BDH) and N-phenylanthranilic acid (Kochlight) were used as such. Anthranilic acid was recrystallised from hot water (m.p. 145°). Ethanol and petroleum ether (40-60°) were purified and dried by usual methods and petroleum ether was stored over sodium.

Preparation of U(IV) and Th(IV) complexes

For the preparation of I to VIII chelates, $U(OAc)_4$ or $Th(OAc)_4$ and α -picolinic acid, nicotinic acid, anthranilic acid or N-phenylanthranilic acid were taken in 1 : 4 stoichiometry and were refluxed (Table 1) in ethanol. On the addition

of petroleum ether the respective chelates got precipitated which were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried under vacuum.

The analytical results are given in Table 1. IR spectra (nujol) of the complexes were recorded on a Specord-71 IR Spectrophotometer. Diffuse reflectance spectra of U(IV) complexes were recorded on a SP-700 Spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibilities of U(IV) chelates were measured at room temperature on a Gouy balance.

Results and Discussion

The chelates of U(IV) are stable at room temperature in stoppered vials and are slowly oxidised by air. All these chelates of U(IV) and Th(IV) do not melt but decompose at higher temperature, giving U_3O_8 and ThO_2 at $\sim 650^\circ$ and $\sim 850^\circ$ respectively. These complexes are insoluble in common organic solvents.

IR spectra of chelates I and II give strong bands at 1630 and 1625 cm^{-1} respectively, indicating that carbonyl oxygen coordinates to U(IV) or Th(IV). This probably forms chelate rings having squareantiprism arrangement about uranium or thorium. IR spectra of nicotinic acid and of chelates III and IV indicate that the bands at 1675, 1640, 1570 cm^{-1}

TABLE—1. CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF THE COMPLEXES

Chelate	Formula	Colour	Refluxing time	%Found			%Calculated				
				U/Th	C	H	N	U/Th	C	H	N
I	$U(C_5H_7NCOO)_4$	Green	1 hr.	32.97	40.10	2.25	7.80	32.79	39.67	2.21	7.71
II	$Th(C_5H_7NCOO)_4$	White	2 hrs.	32.28	39.52	2.16	7.66	32.22	40.00	2.22	7.78
III	$U(OAc)_2(C_5H_7NCOO)_2$	Light green	1 hr.	40.20	32.64	2.40	4.59	39.66	32.00	2.33	4.66
IV	$Th(OAc)_2(C_5H_7NCOO)_2$	White	1 hr.	40.60	32.00	2.31	4.70	39.05	32.32	2.36	4.71
V	$UO(C_5H_7NH_2COO)_2$	Green	4 hrs.	44.46	32.21	2.30	5.42	45.25	31.93	2.28	5.32
VI	$Th(C_5H_7NH_2COO)_4$	Pink	15 min.	30.05	43.35	3.12	7.45	29.89	43.29	3.16	7.22
VII	$UO(C_5H_7NHC_6H_5COO)_2$	Palegreen	5 hrs.	34.69	44.31	2.40	4.50	35.22	45.11	2.66	4.14
VIII	$Th(C_5H_7NHC_6H_5COO)_4$	Yellow	15 min.	21.67	59.10	3.51	5.35	21.56	58.00	3.35	5.21

shift to 1700, 1595 and 1540 cm^{-1} in chelate III and to 1700, 1605 and 1560 cm^{-1} in chelate IV. These shifted bands are probably due to $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{OCO})$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{OCO})$. The band at 1410 cm^{-1} shifts to 1400 cm^{-1} in chelates III and IV. IR spectra thus indicate that carboxylate acts as a bidentate group. However definite assignment cannot be made since acetate and nicotinate group frequencies occur in the same region. IR spectra of anthranilic acid and chelates V and VI record ν_{asym} and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(-\text{NH}_2)$ as broad bands at 3400 and 3300 cm^{-1} . Since the position of the $\nu(\text{N-H})$ remains almost the same in the complexes as in the ligand; N of the $-\text{NH}_2$ does not seem to coordinate to U(IV) or Th(IV). $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{OCO})$ observed at 1670 cm^{-1} in anthranilic acid splits into a shoulder at 1700 and a very strong band at 1670 cm^{-1} in chelate VI. $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{OCO})$ falls to 1395 cm^{-1} , indicating that only one oxygen of the carboxylate ion is coordinated to Th(IV). The $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{OCO})$ at 1670 cm^{-1} is absent in U(IV) chelate. In the IR spectrum of sodium anthranilate,

chelates V and VII are polymeric with

linkages³.

Reflectance spectra of U(IV) chelates (Table 2) belong to the strong intensity type on the classification of Gans and Marriage⁸. Reflectance spectra of U(IV) chelates are similar to spectra of U(IV) compounds where uranium is eight coordinated.^{1,2,3,8}

The μ_{eff} of the chelates I, III, V and VII are 2.35, 1.97, 1.57 and 2.36 BM respectively. The μ_{eff} of 2.35 and 2.36 B.M. for chelates I and VII are comparable to that reported where U(IV) is eight coordinated.^{1,2,3,8} Low values of 1.97 and 1.57 B.M., for the chelates III and V may be due to metal-metal interaction involving oxygen bridging.

TABLE—2. 'STRONG' INTENSITY REFLECTANCE SPECTRA OF U(IV) COMPLEXES IN NM.

Term ^a	Tetrakis (α -picolinato)-uranium(IV)	Disacetatobis-(nicotinato)-uranium(IV)	Oxobis(anthranilato)-uranium(IV)	Oxobis(N-phenylanthranilato)-uranium(IV)
³ F ₂	2000sh	1920b	1930sh	1850sh
³ H ₃	1670m 1500s]	1665w 1490m]	1660m 1490m]	1650w 1520b]
³ F ₃	1400sh	1410sh	1400w	1400w
³ F ₄	1120vs	1110s	1100s	1100vs
³ H ₆	820sh	940sh	820w	840sh 800sh]
³ P ₀ , ¹ G ₄	780sh	665b	660b	720sh 660b]
¹ D ₂	645vs	-	-	-
³ P ₁	560s	520vs	560m	590m
¹ I ₆	480s	425w	-	420s

a = assignments as given in references 2 and 8.

the bands at 1521⁶ and 1398⁷ cm^{-1} have been attributed to $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{OCO})$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{OCO})$ of the carboxylate ion. In chelate V strong bands at 1610 and 1495 cm^{-1} indicate that both oxygen atoms of the carboxylate ion are coordinated to U(IV).

IR spectra of N-phenylanthranilic acid and chelates VII and VIII record that $\nu(\text{N-H})$ remains at the same position indicating that N of the N-phenylanthranilic acid is not coordinated to U(IV) or Th(IV). In chelates VII and VIII bands at 1590, 1390 cm^{-1} and 1585, 1400 cm^{-1} respectively indicate that carboxylate acts as a bidentate group. The

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